

FORMULATION OF POTTING COMPOSTS FOR OPTIMUM GROWTH RATE OF A HIGHLY VALUED TIMBER SPECIES IN NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

This study examined the impact of formulated potting composts on the early growth performance of *Terminalia ivorensis* seedlings. This was done to identify the potting media that could trigger the optimum growth rate of this highly valued timber species for short rotation at the nursery and early introduction to the plantation environment. The experiment was arranged in a completely randomized design (CRD) with seven treatments and 20 replicates per treatment. Growth data such as the seedling's height (cm), collar diameter (mm), and number of leaves per seedling were collected fortnightly. Biomass accumulation by the seedlings was estimated at the end of the experiment. Data collected were subjected to a one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA), while means with significant difference were separated using Duncan's New Multiple Range Test (DMRT). The result reveals significant differences in the seedling's height, collar diameter, leaf count, and biomass accumulation. Seedlings planted in PC2 had the highest seedling height (36.93cm), while seedlings planted in PC4 produced the highest number of leaves (22) and the biggest collar diameter (0.58cm). Generally, the results revealed that *Terminalia ivorensis* seedlings planted in PC4 had the best seedling growth performance. This was followed by seedlings planted in PC2 and PC3 respectively. However, seedlings planted in PC7 had the lowest growth rate. To trigger the optimum growth rate potential of *Terminalia ivorensis* seedlings, PC4 is therefore recommended.

Keywords: potting composts, optimum growth, *Terminalia ivorensis*

Introduction

The regeneration of indigenous tree species has been restricted to natural forests owing to the preference of exotic trees for plantation establishment (Fasalejo et al., 2019). In forest ecosystems, tree species could be classified as indigenous or exotic. A tree is regarded as an indigenous species if it is naturally endemic to a given region or nation without human intervention and as exotic if it is being cultivated outside its natural region (Lawal and Bakare 2020).

Terminalia ivorensis A. Chev is popularly called 'Black Afara' because of its external features (Onyekwelu et al., 2008). It belongs to the family *Combretaceae*. The branches are whorled with young shoots and foliage (Keay, 1989). Its timber, which is suitable for construction, furniture, and veneer, is highly priced for its quality and durability (Akindele and Owoeye, 1991). The

species occurs in evergreen and moist semideciduous forests, where larger trees are most common in low-lying localities or lowlands (Bakshi et al., 1972; Keay, 1989). It is an important timber species both in Africa and beyond. In Nigeria, the demand for *Terminalia ivorensis*, an indigenous tropical hardwood, for export and domestic consumption is increasing, while the natural forest is being depleted as a result of overexploitation. Alamu and Alabi (2015) reported that *Terminalia ivorensis* is threatened by habitat loss.

A mature tree of *Terminalia ivorensis* attains heights of up to 50 m and girths of 5 m, while young trees often attain only 1-1.5 m height after 5 years, compared to some other timber species, which are fast-growing (Ibe et al., 2015). More so, limited studies are available on the application of potting compost from locally sourced agricultural wastes and inorganic fertilizers for enhanced growth performance of *Terminalia ivorensis*. The relative slow growth rate, the threatened status due to habitat loss, and the need to foster the establishment of *Terminalia ivorensis* in plantations as well as improve its regeneration prospects necessitated this study.

Study Area

This study was carried out at the permanent nursery site of the Department of Forestry and Wood Technology, Federal University of Technology Akure, Ondo State, Nigeria. The University is located between latitudes 7°17' and 7°18' N and longitudes 5°06' and 5°09' E, with an altitude of 350 m above sea level. The rainfall pattern of the study area is bimodal, with a mean annual rainfall of about 2000mm. The mean annual humidity is about 80%, while the mean daily temperature is about 26°C.

Seed Collection and germination study

Mature seeds of *Terminalia ivorensis* were collected from the OA3 forest reserve in Ore Local Government, Ondo State, Nigeria. Three hundred (300) seeds of *Terminalia ivorensis* were broadcast on a germination bed. Periodic watering was done to ensure maximum seed germination.

Collection of materials for compost production

Cow dung and poultry droplets used for this study were collected from the animal farm section of the teaching and research farm at the Federal University of Technology, Akure, Ondo State, Nigeria. After collection, they were sun-dried for 5 days, crushed into smaller particles using a mortar and pestle, and sieved. Topsoil was locally sourced and NPK fertilizer was also purchased from a reputable chemical vendor.

Formulated Potting compost for improved growth performance of *Terminalia ivorensis*

PC1 = 15g cow dung + 2kg topsoil

PC2 = 30g cow dung + 2kg topsoil

PC3= 15g poultry manure + 2kg topsoil

PC4 = 30g poultry manure + 2kg topsoil

PC5 = 5g NPK+2kg topsoil

PC6 = 10g NPK+2kg topsoil

PC7 = 2 kg topsoil without fertilizer (Control).

After composition, samples from each compost were taken to the lab for nutrient composition determination.

Data collection

After seed germination, seedlings of fairly uniform size (height) with two leaves were pricked-out and transplanted into the already prepared polythene pots containing the different potting composts (treatments). The Experiment was arranged in a Completely Randomized Design (CRD) with 7 treatments and 20 replicates per treatment. The seedlings growth performance was measured fortnightly. The experiment lasted for 24 weeks. The variables measured include the total height (cm) of the seedlings, the total number of leaves, and Collar diameter (cm). The seedlings height and collar diameter were measured with a ruler and venier caliper, respectively, while the number of leaves were virtually counted

Method of Data Analysis

The data on seedling early growth assessment and biomass were subjected to a one-way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) to compare the effect of the composts on the early growth performance of *Terminalia ivorensis* seedlings. Treatment means found to differ significantly were separated using the Duncan Multiple Range Test (DMRT), and their results were summarized in tables and figures. More so, percentage difference between the control (PC7) and other potting composts is calculated as follow:

$$\text{Percentage difference (\%)} = \frac{\text{Variable measured for other treatment} - \text{Variable measured for control}}{\text{Variable measured for Control}} \times 100$$

RESULTS

The nutrient composition of the potting media used in this study is presented in Table 1. The laboratory result revealed that the nitrogen concentration in the seven treatments was similar but higher in PC4 (0.22 g/kg), while the phosphorus and potassium concentrations were much higher in PC6 (72.54 mg/kg and 1.17 mol/kg, respectively).

Table 1: Nutrient Composition of the Potting Media

Treatment	Nitrogen (g/kg)	Phosphorus (mg/kg)	Potassium (mol/kg)
PC ₁	0.18 ^a	19.55 ^f	0.28 ^c
PC ₂	0.21 ^a	40.23 ^d	0.44 ^c
PC ₃	0.21 ^a	42.80 ^c	0.51 ^b
PC ₄	0.22 ^a	38.95 ^c	0.64 ^b
PC ₅	0.18 ^a	49.93 ^b	0.75 ^b
PC ₆	0.18 ^a	72.54 ^a	1.17 ^a
PC ₇	0.21 ^a	9.78 ^g	0.34 ^c

Means with the same superscripts in the same column are not significantly different (P<0.05)

Seedlings Growth Characteristics

Leaf production pattern of *Terminalia ivorensis* in the formulated potting composts

The result in Figure 1, seedlings planted in CP4, seedlings with the highest number of leaves, showed an increasing number of leaves with an increasing number of weeks until the 13th week of growth, when no increment was recorded. However, a marginal increment was seen in the 22nd week of growth. A seedling planted in PC2 was next to seedlings planted in PC4 in terms of leaf production. More so, a similar leaf production pattern was found in the seedlings planted in this potting compost (CP2). Seedlings planted in PC1, PC3, and PC6 had similar leaf production patterns, as revealed in the figure (Fig. 1). Leaf production by the seedlings planted in PC5 does not show a significant increase in leaf production through the growth period. A similar trend was observed in seedlings planted in PC7, except for an abrupt increase in leaf production towards the end of the growing period. Generally, leaf production increased more steadily in seedlings planted in PC4. This was relatively followed by the seedlings planted in PC2, PC1, and PC7, and the least leaf production was found in seedlings planted in PC7.

Figure 1: Leaf production pattern of *Terminalia ivorensis* seedlings in different potting composts

The result of the analysis of variance (ANOVA) revealed a significant difference ($P \leq 0.05$) in the number of leaves produced by *Terminalia ivorensis* seedlings in different potting composts. In this study, leaf production by *Terminalia ivorensis* seedlings was significantly higher in PC4 and PC2. These potting composts produced seedlings that were 72.56% and 71.38% higher than the number of leaves produced by the seedling planted in CP7 (control). The number of leaves produced by seedlings planted in PC1, PC3 and PC6 was statistically similar, as presented in the table. More so, PC5 and PC7 produced seedlings with a statistically similar number of leaves.

Table 2: Effect of Potting compost on number of leaves of *Terminalia ivorensis* seedlings

Treatment	Mean number of leaves	Percentage difference (%)
PC4	21.95 ^a	72.56
PC 2	21.80 ^a	71.38
PC1	17.50 ^{ab}	37.58
PC6	16.94 ^{ab}	33.18
PC3	16.54 ^{ab}	30.03
PC5	13.33 ^b	4.80
PC7	12.72 ^b	0

Means with the same superscripts in the same column are not significantly different ($P < 0.05$)

Height Growth pattern of *Terminalia ivorensis* in the formulated potting composts

The graphical presentation of the height growth pattern of *Terminalia ivorensis* seedlings is presented in Figure 2. Although the seedlings height growth in all the potting composts increased by weeks, a more pronounced height growth was found in PC2 and PC4. PC1 and PC3 had similar height growth patterns, while seedlings planted in PC7 had the lowest growth rate.

Figure 2: Height growth pattern of *Terminalia ivorensis* seedlings in different potting composts

The effect of potting compost on the seedling height of *Terminalia ivorensis* is presented in Table 3. The result reveals a significant difference in seedling height among the potting composts. PC2 was discovered to have the highest seedling height (36.93cm). This was closely followed by PC4 (35.12cm), PC3 (31.08cm) and PC3 (29.24cm) respectively. Seedlings planted in PC6, PC5 and PC7 were found to be statistically the same as presented in Table 3. Seedlings planted in PC2, PC4 and PC3 were found to be 103.25%, 93.29% and 71.05% respectively, faster in height growth than seedlings planted in CP7.

Table 3: Effect of potting composts on the seedling height of *Terminalia ivorensis*

Treatment	Mean seedling height (cm)	Percentage difference (%)
PC2	36.93 ^a	103.25
PC4	35.12 ^{ab}	93.29
PC3	31.08 ^{bc}	71.05
PC1	29.24 ^c	60.92
PC6	23.06 ^d	26.91
PC5	22.57 ^d	24.22
PC7	18.17 ^d	0.00

Means with the same superscripts in the same column are not significantly different (P<0.05)

Collar Diameter Growth pattern of *Terminalia ivorensis* in the formulated potting composts

The growth pattern with respect to collar diameter for *Terminalia ivorensis* seedlings planted in different potting composts for 24 weeks is presented in Figure 3. Generally, seedling collar diameter increased steadily with weeks. However, more growth per week was recorded for PC1 and PC4 respectively.

Figure 3: Collar diameter growth pattern in *Terminalia ivorensis* seedlings in different potting composts

The effect of potting composts on collar diameter differs significantly (Table 4). Seedlings planted in PC4 had collar diameters that were significantly higher than those planted in other potting composts. Also, seedlings planted in PC4 were found to grow 56.76% faster in collar diameter than the control. Statistically, a significant difference was not recorded for seedlings planted in PC2, PC3 and PC6. However, the collar diameter for seedlings planted in PC1 was significantly higher than those planted in PC5 and PC7 as presented in Table 4.

Table 4: Effects of potting compost on seedlings collar diameter of *Terminalia ivorensis*

Treatment	Mean Collar Diameter (cm)	Percentage difference (%)
PC4	0.58 ^a	56.76
PC2	0.56 ^{ab}	51.35
PC3	0.51 ^{ab}	37.84
PC6	0.50 ^{ab}	35.14
PC1	0.49 ^b	32.43
PC5	0.39 ^c	5.41

PC7	0.37 ^c	0.00
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Values in the same column followed by the same alphabet are not significantly different (P<0.05)

DISCUSSION

Many tropical timber species in Nigeria are currently threatened with extinction owing to habitat destruction, polycyclic logging, and selective logging (Lawal et al., 2019). Plantations of many of these highly valued timber species rarely exist. Hence, their sustainability and continuous existence are at the mercy of nature and protection efforts by governmental and non-governmental organizations. In Nigeria and other tropical countries, several forest regeneration methods have been attempted. Natural regeneration, which has been used, is a process whereby the forest is allowed to grow back to its original state unaided. This process failed, and an attempt was made to enrich the forest by planting desired seedlings (Ehiagbonare, 2006). Many tropical timber species rarely flower, and when they do, abortion and destruction of mature fruits by biotic agents are eminent. Ehiagbonare (2006) revealed that many tropical hardwoods produce seeds very erratically, and seeds often fail to germinate. Although schemes to replace the destroyed forests cannot keep pace with the destruction, new forest plantations usually rely on exotic species like *Tectona grandis*, *Gmelina aborea*, and *Eucalyptus* species introduced because they grow faster than the native hardwoods like *Terminalia ivorensis*, *Terminalia superba*, and *Nauclea diderrichii* (Ehiagbonare, 2006). Production of tree seedlings with adaptable nursery techniques for enhanced growth rates will further encourage forest managers to domesticate and establish plantations of indigenous tree species in Nigeria.

Productions of healthy and vigorous seedlings of different tropical tree species have been traced back to the application of organic manure in the nursery stage (Fagbenro, 1995; Orwa et al., 2009; and Awotoye, 2019). In this study, formulated potting composts triggered leaf production in *Terminalia ivorensis* by 72.56% compared to seedlings planted in top soil, a common potting medium for raising seedlings in Nigeria. In tree seedlings, more leaf production could translate to more food production through photosynthesis and consequently result in an improved growth rate. According to Burdett (1983), phenotypic traits created during nursery culture can be as important as genetic traits in determining initial field performance. This assertion was confirmed in studies showing that the initial field performance of seedlings from improved genetic sources was limited because nursery culture resulted in poor phenotypic traits (Grossnickle and Major, 1994).

Puttonen (1997) opined that morphological attributes are reliable measures of seedling quality because they are retained for extended timeframes after seedlings are outplanted. Diane (2008) revealed that shoot height is correlated to the number of needles on the seedling and therefore provides an estimate of photosynthetic capacity and transpirational area. Taller seedlings may have an advantage against severe weed competition and may indicate superior genetics. Shoot

height in tree seedlings could be affected by different potting composts, as revealed in this study. Accordingly, height growth in *Terminalia ivirensis* seedlings planted in formulated potting media was significantly higher than that in topsoil. Specifically, seedlings planted in PC4 were 72.6% better than those planted in topsoil. The reasons for the better height growth of seedlings planted in this formulated potting compost (PC4) could be attributed to the higher concentrations of nitrogen, phosphorus, and potassium. This finding is supported by Donkor (1997), who found out that organic materials are major sources of nitrogen (N), phosphorous (P), and sulfur (S).

Seedling height has been discovered to have a positive impact on the successful establishment of seedlings when planted out. Pinto et al., (2015) pointed out that seedling height at planting can forecast growth because taller seedlings keep their height advantage over time. Thiffault *et al.* (2014) revealed that this height advantage is beneficial when seedlings are planted on sites with competing vegetation. According to del Campo et al., (2010), seedlings with a greater initial height can subsequently have greater shoot-system development due to a greater number of branches, buds, and foliage in hardwoods. As a result, such seedlings have a greater photosynthetically active surface area (Luis et al., 2009). A positive relationship between initial seedling height and subsequent height growth has been reported in several studies (Pinto et al., 2015; Deligoz et al., 2013; Regan et al., 2015; Akpo et al., 2014; and Clark et al., 2016).

Another morphological trait that should not be overlooked is seedling collar diameter. Seedling collar diameter was triggered by 56.76% in PC4 as revealed in this study. This implies that greater collar diameter could be achieved with formulated potting compost to enhance seedling survival and successful establishment in the field. Stem diameter has been considered the best predictor of field survival and growth, as a larger diameter also indicates a larger root system and a larger stem volume (South and Rakestraw, 2002). Steven et al., (2017) confirmed that initial stem diameter is considered the best morphological attribute to forecast future growth because it correlates with seedling weight and root system size. Jaghagen and Albrekton (1996) opined that initial seedling size in terms of collar diameter can have a long-lasting effect on field growth. In their study, seedlings that were larger at planting had greater height and diameter 32–37 years after planting. Several studies have also revealed a positive relationship between initial stem diameter and growth after planting (Jacobs et al., 2005; Semerci 2005; Mexal et al., 2008; Bayala et al., 2009; Li et al., 2011; Clark et al., 2016; and Ivetic et al., 2016).

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

This study reveals that the growth rate of *Terminalia ivorensis* could be triggered by the formulated composts. Formulated compost, PC4, increased the height growth of this species by 72.56%, collar diameter by 56.76%, and leaf production by 103.25%, respectively. Topsoil (PC7), which served as the control, had slow growth on the *Terminalia ivorensis* seedlings. However, the combination of 30g of poultry droplets with 2kg of topsoil (PC4) is highly recommended, as they perform better than all other formulated potting composts used.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that there is no conflict of interest regarding the publishing of the paper by the Biological Research and Biotechnology.

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